

Security Orchestration in 5G and Beyond Smart Network Technologies

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ABSTRACT Security Orchestration (SCO) represents a pivotal element in achieving intelligent and automated security monitoring and management within intricate and dynamic network environments, notably the 5th Generation (5G) and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks. The seamless integration of SCO into emerging 5G/B5G technologies, such as Open Radio Access Networks (ORAN), Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM), Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV), Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), cloud computing, and Network Slicing (NS), is of paramount importance for realizing the vision of zero-touch, self-repair, self-healing, and secure networks. Furthermore, these advanced technologies offer opportunities to enhance SCO's functionalities. This article offers an in-depth exploration of SCO's evolution, significance, functionalities, and critical components, considering its potential within the realm of 5G and B5G network technologies. The primary objective of this specify is to provide an informative analysis of the integration of SCO into 5G and B5G network technologies and how these implementations can be harmoniously combined within a unified framework. Lastly, we present valuable insights, remaining research problems, and future directions toward achieving the goal of zero-touch security and networks.

INDEX TERMS 5G and beyond, security and privacy, security orchestration, zero-touch networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network security can be described as protecting the network's vital assets and data that flows through while understanding, managing, controlling, and minimizing the risk [1]. Network security breaches can jeopardize the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data. These breaches can have serious organizational and socio-economic impacts, including loss of revenue, damage to reputation and information systems and theft of confidential consumer information [2]. Different security measures can suppress known and unidentified attacks and avoid the negative effects that are often associated with security risks and vulnerabilities. These include Security

Information and Event Management (SIEM), Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), firewalls, Intrusion Prevention Systems (IPS) and antivirus [3]. New requirements for increased performance, user-friendliness, flexibility and energy efficiency of emerging network services are expected in advanced mobile networks [4]. At the same time, the threat landscape has evolved with ever more sophisticated attack scenarios and potent attackers. Starting from the early networks, the security environment for telecommunication networks has evolved and developed in parallel with the 1st Generation (1G), 2nd Generation (2G), 3rd Generation (3G), 4G and 5G and beyond technologies [5]. 1G is an analogue cellular phone, which

is therefore very insecure. There were no explicit security mechanisms, so privacy issues such as illegal cloning and masquerading were a major problem [6], [7]. As telecommunication technologies have evolved from 2G to 5G, network security has evolved and introduced methods such as secure access, Authentication and Key Agreements (AKA), two-way authentication, new encryption, trust and integrity protection mechanisms to ensure security in mobile networks [8]. These security solutions use different technologies and frameworks. Therefore, integrated and well-connected security solutions are difficult to realize. To close this gap, SCO can play an important role. It aims to integrate different security solutions in a smooth and coordinated way to improve overall security and minimize human involvement. The demand for automated security is driving the popularity of SCO. Moreover, the increasing role and importance of SCO signify a rising global market share. SCO market size was valued at USD 1.45 Billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 4.63 Billion by 2028, growing at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 15.60 from 2021 to 2028 [9].

A. WHY SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IS NEEDED IN B5G

1) SECURITY IN B5G

5G aims to support enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication (uRLLC) and massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) [10]. At the same time, 5G enables new applications such as the Internet of Things (IoT), autonomous vehicles (AV), augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), mixed reality (MR) and Industry 4.0 [11]. B5G networks create an all-dimensional, user-centric information ecosystem that connects all elements of our future society [12]. However, this development requires a number of complex requirements that can be categorized into user performance and system and management perspectives. These include energy and cost efficiency, massive connectivity, flexibility, programmability, spectrum efficiency, ultra-reliability and availability, seamless mobility, ultra-low latency, high data rates and enhanced security and privacy [13].

To meet these complex requirements, 5G relies on a new paradigm for computing and infrastructure. Open RAN (ORAN), Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM), Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV), cloud computing, edge computing and Network Slicing (NS) enable rapid operational changes, optimized use of network resources and fast service provisioning cycles. SDN and NFV enable the automation of the provision and management of network services through the virtualization of network functions. Hardware networks are transformed into software-based networks. In addition to the physical infrastructure, virtual slices must also be created and managed to ensure End-to-End (E2E) security. E2E network security encompasses both the security of virtual and physical resources and the security of end users [14]. The three main components of B5G network security are as

follows: The first component is the pre-5G security threats and requirements. The second component is the security and privacy issues arising from network softwarization and the deployment of new technologies such as SDN, NFV, MEC and NS. The third component is the security issues associated with the massive number of users, the diversity of connected devices and services, the privacy concerns associated with new users and stakeholders, and the security requirements of mission-critical applications and IoT [15], [16]. As described in Section II-A, some of the 5G and B5G security issues are secure transmission, message authentication, key distribution, device identification and privacy computation.

The increasing complexity of 5G/B5G network architectures, driven by softwarization, virtualization and multi-domain orchestration, poses significant security challenges that existing mechanisms struggle to address. Emerging technologies such as ORAN, SDN, NFV, MEC and ZSM enable dynamic and flexible network management, but also increase the attack surface by increasing the number of open interfaces, software-based control mechanisms and distributed network elements [17]. NS, a key enabler of 5G services, brings unique security challenges, including inter-slice isolation, cross-slice attacks and the need for dynamic enforcement of security policies [18]. In addition, MEC and edge computing bring computing and storage capacity closer to end users, improving performance but also exposing critical infrastructure to potential security breaches and low-latency attacks [19]. Traditional security mechanisms such as static firewall policies, perimeter-based defenses and manually configured security functions, are not sufficient to defend against dynamic real-time security threats in B5G environments [20]. Legacy security solutions lack adaptability, automation and closed-loop threat response. This makes them ineffective against sophisticated attackers using AI-driven attacks, advanced persistent threats (APTs) and zero-day vulnerabilities. To address these issues, there is an urgent need for a unified SCO framework that integrates real-time monitoring, automated incident response, and AI-driven threat intelligence. An SCO-enabled approach would facilitate E2E security automation, ensuring that threats are detected, analyzed, and mitigated dynamically while maintaining policy consistency across SDN/NFV, MEC, and NS environments. By leveraging AI/ML-based security analytics, SCO can enable predictive threat mitigation, anomaly detection, and adaptive security enforcement, addressing the shortcomings of existing 5G/B5G security frameworks.

2) WHY NOT CONVENTIONAL SECURITY SOLUTIONS

Despite advances in Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks, existing architectures such as ETSI NFV MANO and 3GPP NS management face significant limitations in addressing the dynamic and evolving security challenges in 5G/B5G networks. A major shortcoming is the lack of security automation and closed-loop orchestration, which is

critical for mitigating real-time threats in virtualized environments [21]. Traditional MANO frameworks focus primarily on managing the life-cycle of Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs), but do not provide built-in mechanisms for real-time security monitoring and automated threat response, making them unsuitable for addressing security threats in dynamic SDN/NFV-based architectures [22]. Additionally, existing frameworks struggle with enforcing consistent security policies across heterogeneous network domains, especially in multi-tenant NS scenarios, where cross-slice attacks and misconfigurations can lead to security breaches [23]. Another critical issue is the lack of coordination between different security enforcement points across cloud, edge, and RAN environments, making it difficult to establish an E2E security framework [17]. Furthermore, MANO architectures do not natively support AI/ML-based security analytics, limiting their ability to dynamically adapt to emerging threats [24]. These shortcomings highlight the need for an advanced SCO framework that integrates automated security enforcement, real-time monitoring and cross-domain security coordination to ensure robust protection for the entire 5G/B5G ecosystem.

These complex security and privacy concerns of 5G and B5G cannot be met by pre-5G security measures and mechanisms. Manually handling security in 5G and B5G is an arduous task given the complexity and volume of connected devices and can lead to significant human error. In addition, the evolution of malware and sophisticated network topology make it difficult to detect threats that require highly intelligent and adaptive security monitoring and management systems. Novel 5G use cases and applications such as IoT, Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle to Everything (V2X) will introduce a huge number of diverse communicating devices [8]. This makes the threat landscape very dynamic and requires real-time threat detection, response and mitigation, which is not possible with traditional solutions. Traditional security solutions lack a holistic view of the network and context awareness, which is even more important in 5G networks due to the dynamic and automated provisioning, orchestration and management of networks. 5G and B5G technologies such as SDN, NFV and edge/cloud computing could be leveraged to improve security operations, which is not yet the case with traditional security solutions [25]. Apart from that, it is difficult to meet the scalability, accuracy, reliability and efficiency requirements of 5G and B5G security with conventional solutions [26], [27]. Resources such as computing power, storage and bandwidth have become increasingly expensive and scarce, especially towards the edge where 5G and B5G intend to support latency-critical applications, including IoT, V2V and V2X [8], [28]. Dynamic resource allocation is vital for security in 5G and B5G so that security management does not overload the services and applications. Therefore, traditional security solutions in 5G cannot be used efficiently and effectively to achieve the desired level of security and a novel framework is needed.

3) SCO AS A GAME CHANGER FOR SECURITY IN 5G AND B5G NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES

The SCO framework is able to dynamically detect, respond to, prevent and mitigate cyberattacks by installing and configuring the necessary configuration rules for security/network functions in the right place at the right time. At the same time, it can provide the network administrator with valuable insights into performance metrics and network updates in real time, allowing for human intervention when needed. Emerging 5G and B5G technologies such as ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, edge computing and NS can be used in SCO to introduce new security features and provide the scalability and flexibility required for 5G and B5G. SCO can leverage means of AI/ML to detect and respond to security threats long before they cause damage. In addition, various dimensions of DLT could be leveraged by SCO to improve trust and privacy in communication across boundaries and interfaces. Furthermore, user-defined high-level policy models serve as input for the SCO framework and leave rule-based security management behind. SCO is able to automate provisioning and must act as part of the network (built-in). The ultimate goal of SCO in 5G and B5G is to achieve self-healing and self-repairing zero-touch networks through on-demand security provisioning and dynamic defence against cyberattacks depending on the actual context [29]. Context-aware, holistic SCO could overcome the challenges described in Section I-A.2. SCO is able to support intelligent and automated security monitoring and management while orchestrating the underlying network infrastructure and functions.

4) SECURITY CONSIDERATIONS IN STANDARDIZATION BODIES

Security in 5G/B5G networks is an important focus for standardization bodies such as ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute), 3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project) and IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force). These organizations define security architectures, requirements and best practices to ensure robust protection in virtualized, software-defined and multi-tenant network environments. This section provides an overview of the key security guidelines from ETSI NFV, ETSI MEC, 3GPP and IETF, highlighting their importance for SCO in 5G/B5G ecosystems.

The ETSI NFV (Network Function Virtualization) group addresses security concerns in virtualized network environments. ETSI GS NFV-SEC 001 provides a security problem statement, identifying risks related to VNF isolation, hypervisor security, and software-defined security management [30]. ETSI GS NFV-SEC 012 focuses on security monitoring and orchestration, proposing a security management framework for automated security enforcement in NFV infrastructures [31]. Despite these efforts, security orchestration in NFV MANO remains a challenge, requiring cross-domain policy enforcement and real-time security automation. MEC

(Multi-access Edge Computing) introduces new attack surfaces due to its distributed nature. ETSI MEC addresses security challenges in MEC, including data privacy, access control, and isolation mechanisms for edge computing [32]. The 3GPP security architecture for 5G (TS 33.501) establishes fundamental security mechanisms [33]. The IETF has also published multiple RFCs related to security in SDN, NFV, and cloud-native networking [34].

Additionally, open-source frameworks such as OpenStack, Kubernetes, and OSM have implemented security features that contribute to practical SCO solutions. OpenStack provides keystone for identity management and Security Groups for network-based access control [35]. Kubernetes integrates RBAC (Role-Based Access Control) and Pod Security Policies to enforce secure containerized deployments [36]. Open Source MANO (OSM) enhances security automation in NFV orchestration, including secure VNF instantiation and policy-driven access control [37]. To summarize, while ETSI NFV, ETSI MEC, 3GPP and IETF have provided essential security guidelines, current standards lack comprehensive SCO mechanisms that enable real-time autonomous security enforcement. Open source communities such as OpenStack, Kubernetes and OSM provide practical implementations, but their security mechanisms remain isolated across domains. Closing these gaps requires a holistic SCO framework that integrates security automation, cross-domain policy orchestration and AI-driven threat intelligence into existing standardization efforts.

B. ARTICLE MOTIVATION

In this survey, we provide an overview of SCO as a framework in 5G and B5G with components and functionalities. We then discuss and understand how SCO can be successfully implemented in 5G and B5G network technologies such as ORAN, ZSM, SND, NFV, NS, and cloud/edge computing. To achieve this goal, we consider the contributions from academia and industry focusing on the implementation of SCO tailored to 5G and B5G network technologies and use cases. In addition, attention has been paid to the technical challenges and enabling technologies when SCO meets 5G and B5G network technologies. 5G and B5G security has gained importance in communications research [8], [15]. However, the research community has not yet comprehensively discussed or researched SCO in 5G and B5G technologies, and the focus is slowly shifting towards SCO. After an extensive search, we were able to categorize the existing related surveys, focusing on surveys about SCO in 5G and B5G technologies [38].

There are not many papers in this category that deal with SCO in 5G and B5G technologies. SCO in 5G and B5G technologies is much more complicated than SCO in traditional IT infrastructures due to softwarization, heterogeneity, strict use case requirements, the number of connected devices and the huge traffic volume. Zheng et al. [38] focus on Security Automation (SA) and SCO in IoT environments. Nerijus et al. [39] review security challenges of fog computing and the security challenges of orchestration. The authors identify that

TABLE 1. An Overview of Significant Surveys on SCO

Ref.	Role of SCO	SCO in 5G and B5G	Research Directions	Remarks
[3]	H	L	M	Surveys SCO in organizations and enterprises, focusing on main functionalities, core components, key drivers, and SCO taxonomy. Does not cover 5G technologies or SCO in 5G/B5G.
[40]	M	L	H	A survey on Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response (SOAR) solutions from an AI/ML perspective in organizations. Does not cover SCO in 5G/B5G.
[38]	M	M	H	Discusses challenges and advancements in SCO for IoT systems and future directions. Does not cover SCO in 5G/B5G.
[41]	L	L	L	Examines autonomous anomaly management using ML. Does not cover SCO in 5G/B5G.
[42]	H	L	L	Analyzes automation in information security management, but does not discuss SCO in 5G/B5G.
[43]	M	L	H	Discusses limitations, design guidelines, and research directions for automating end-user security, but lacks 5G/B5G coverage.
[44]	L	L	M	Outlines security applications for automation in information security management. Does not include 5G/B5G.
[45]	H	L	L	Highlights the importance, role, and elements of SCO in IT while listing automation tools. Does not cover SCO in 5G/B5G.
[46]	H	L	M	Demonstrates current gaps and issues in the SCO field and suggests future directions. Does not discuss SCO in 5G/B5G.
[47]	M	L	L	Surveys AI/ML/DL automation technologies for security but does not discuss SCO in 5G/B5G.
This paper	H	H	H	A comprehensive survey of SCO in 5G/B5G technologies, including role, enabling technologies and research directions.

L Low Coverage M Medium Coverage H High Coverage

security and privacy are critical in fog computing orchestration. In this article, however, no special attention is paid to SCO or SCO challenges in fog computing. As summarized in Table 1, none of these studies cover the holistic picture of SCO in 5G and B5G technologies by looking at the background, development, functionalities and components. Our main motivation is to investigate how SCO can support security management in 5G and B5G technologies using enabling technologies, potential problems and solutions, while identifying the areas for future research.

C. ARTICLE CONTRIBUTION

This article stands as a pioneering effort as it is the first study to explore the fusion of SCO with 5G and B5G technologies, including ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, MEC/edge computing and NS. This study highlights the need to create a SCO framework equipped with universal knowledge and a holistic network perspective, and aims to pave the way for the realization of future zero-touch networks. The main objective of this work is to broaden the landscape of SCO in 5G and B5G networks and enable the interworking of novel technologies for better security management, while identifying a potential

SCO framework for 5G and B5G networks. The following is a summary of this article's significant contributions:

- In-depth investigation of the role of SCO with a focus on novel technologies and the paradigm of softwarization in the context of 5G/B5G.
- Comprehensive exploration of how SCO can be integrated and implemented in 5G/B5G technologies such as ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, NS, and edge/cloud computing, considering key design insights and future research direction.
- Highlighting the lesson learned for all of the above key areas, identifying remaining research problems and suggesting future research directions in the light of the knowledge gained from the survey.

This survey not only broadens the understanding of SCO in 5G/B5G technologies but also serves as a compass guiding future research endeavors in the pursuit of robust SCO frameworks. This article's organization is as follows: This article's motivation and overall contribution are highlighted in Section I. Section II discusses how SCO can be integrated into 5G/B5G network technologies. Section III discusses SCO in SDN, Section IV presents SCO in NFV, Section V provides SCO role in NS. Section VI discusses SCO in cloud/MEC computing. Section VII presents SCO in O-RAN. Section VIII details SCO in ZSM. Section IX summarizes the lessons learned and future research directions. In the last section, we conclude the survey.

II. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN 5G AND B5G TECHNOLOGIES

As outlined in Section I-A, the stringent reliability and latency requirements of E2E users necessitate the utilization of various technologies in the innovative architecture of 5G. In this context, SCO plays a critical role in safeguarding networks and data in 5G and beyond 5G (B5G) networks. However, realising a unified SCO framework for both 5G and B5G is an immensely difficult undertaking due to the scale, complexity and heterogeneity of these technologies, some of which have limited synergy or cooperation. Given this complexity, we focus here on how SCO can be effectively implemented as a standalone solution in 5G and B5G-enabled technologies. Specifically, this section covers several key 5G and B5G technologies, including ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, NS, and cloud/edge computing. We introduce security issues within the 5G/B5G landscape and then discuss how these issues can be effectively addressed by implementing SCO.

SDN decouples the control plane from the data plane, enabling centralized management and programmability of network behavior [48]. NFV virtualizes network services traditionally run on proprietary hardware, improving scalability and flexibility by allowing them to operate on standard servers [49]. NS enables the creation of multiple virtual networks on shared physical infrastructure, each tailored to specific application requirements [50]. MEC reduces latency by bringing compute, storage, and networking closer to end users, improving real-time application performance and supporting IoT,

AR/VR, and 5G use cases [51]. Fog computing extends cloud capabilities to the edge, focusing on processing data near its source to improve latency-sensitive applications, while cloud computing offers centralized delivery of computing resources over the internet to provide flexibility and innovation. Edge computing similarly reduces latency by placing computation and storage closer to data sources or end users. O-RAN (Open Radio Access Network) promotes open, interoperable interfaces within the RAN, fostering flexibility and vendor diversity [52]. ZSM framework aims at automating network and service management operations with minimal human intervention [53].

A. INTRODUCTION TO 5G/B5G SECURITY ISSUES

5G supported diverse application scenarios which need secure communication systems. However, due to the complex 6G ecosystem with many new players and a rapid increase of connected devices, pre-6G security issues still exist with a novel set of challenges. Previously, 5G introduced a new set of security issues that did not exist before [6]. (i) To achieve the capabilities that 5G expected to bring, 5G networks supported denser device configurations, higher communication rates, and lower latency. Data transmission can be subjected to more serious issues due to the high density of devices and huge traffic generated. Some of the vulnerabilities are eavesdropping, impersonation attacks, active attacks on traffic data and active attacks on control data [54]. Public key cryptography and symmetric encryption at the upper layers of the protocol stack has been used to achieve secure transmission [55]. Cryptographic approaches are based on computational complexity and are, thereby, potentially not suitable for low-power scenarios such as IoT. Physical Layer Security (PLS) solutions can be utilized to realise keyless secure transmission [55]. Energy-efficient secure transmission is still a major security issue in 5G and B5G networks. (ii) Both entity authentication and message authentication has been really important in 5G wireless networks [56]. Authentication ensures two main security concerns in the communication process. First, the communication originated from the entity that it claims to be, and second, the message has not been altered or substituted by some other party. The existing authentication techniques have limitations in practice, such as high communication and computation costs during the authentication [57]. Moreover, with strict requirements of energy efficiency, spectral efficiency and latency, authentication schemes need to be more efficient in 5G than ever before. (iii) The security of wireless communications is heavily dependent on cryptographic schemes and protocols. Here, secret key distribution is very crucial [58]. The heterogeneous nature, weakly structured architecture and ultra-low latency requirements of 5G networks make it really difficult to distribute and manage the secret keys [55]. Some of the challenges in the key distribution in 5G and B5G networks might be emerging quantum computing-based attacks, the introduction of latency which may not meet the ultra-low latency requirements, the heterogeneous nature of IoT devices and the requirement for public key infrastructure in many

5G applications like device-to-device (D2D) communications [58]. (iv) Device Identification: 5G enables a fully connected society supporting various use cases and applications while billions of devices will be connected to the network [59]. Device identification is required for smooth network monitoring, management, and security. In particular, low-power devices such as IoT are prone to attacks as any other device but lack computational power for cybersecurity software. Therefore, those need closer monitoring to prevent and detect attacks and threats or isolate malfunctioning devices by restricting communication. There are several challenges in device identification, such as the huge volume of devices in cross-system and cross-platform situations, as well as the diversity of types, and ensure that the devices can be quickly and accurately searched [60]. To realize smooth and secure network administration in 5G and B5G networks, device identification is really essential [61]. (v) With the evolution of communication technologies, there are new players in the communication ecosystem, such as cloud computing, big data, and IoT. These technologies require the exchange of huge amounts of personal information across information systems. Therefore, traditional privacy-preserving methods might not be enough and are no longer useful. Privacy computing intends to solve these issues by developing a paradigm of systematic data protection and techniques [62]. Privacy computing can be described as a computing theory and methodology which defines the operations performed on private information during the processing of information. It includes a set of algorithms, theories and application technologies which support the integration of multiple information systems [63].

B. SECURITY ISSUES IN 5G/B5G SYSTEMS

5G/B5G systems face critical security challenges in areas such as secure transmission, message authentication, key distribution, device identification and privacy computing. Technologies such as ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, NS, and edge computing address these issues with innovative solutions. Secure transmission is enhanced by encryption, blockchain and virtualized security functions, while message authentication uses methods such as MAC algorithms, digital signatures and lightweight authentication protocols. Key distribution relies on technologies such as Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), Trusted Platform Modules (TPM) and blockchain-based smart contracts to ensure secure key sharing. Device identification is enhanced by blockchain, monitoring agents and RFID tags, although there are still gaps in certain technologies. Privacy computing uses zero-trust networks, Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) and virtualized privacy enforcement mechanisms to protect sensitive data. Together, these technologies provide a layered approach to securing 5G/B5G infrastructures against evolving threats.

C. INTRODUCTION TO 5G/B5G KEY TECHNOLOGIES

Open RAN (ORAN) introduces more flexibility and openness to Radio Access Network (RAN) deployment. ORAN intends to define interfaces and architecture that enable the

inter-operation between different vendor equipment and lower the cost [64]. Due to the integration of multi-vendor RAN, ORAN will make RAN business more open by offering new opportunities to different vendors and stakeholders to develop RAN in an open ecosystem. Apart from all these advantages, ORAN brings novel security and privacy challenges as well. If not managed carefully, those could lead to huge security and privacy issues. ZSM adapts automation into network service management. 5G and B5G networks are extremely complex and intend to support new business-oriented services. These networks are difficult to be managed by traditional MANO approaches. To support complex requirements and improve performances, ZSM offers efficient network resource management and performance enhancement and ultimately enables a fully automated zero-touch network based on service level policies [65].

In order to enhance features such as enhanced performance, portability, elasticity, and energy efficiency, 5G mobile networks incorporate new networking concepts [4]. The research community and the industry have given significant attention to a few key novel concepts, including ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, NS, and cloud/MEC computing. SDN suggests separating networking devices' control and data planes [66]. It introduces a logically centralized controller with global intelligence. The control functions and business application layer can benefit from the controller's abstract view of the underlying network infrastructure. SDN security is tightly coupled to the controller, and one potential single point of failure is the controller. Failure of the controller can severely affect not only network security but also whole functionality [67]. Therefore, the integration of SCO into SDN is crucial to address the above-mentioned challenges. SCO and SDN could benefit each other with their unique capabilities. The idea of NFV is to operate network functions as virtual instances by separating them from proprietary hardware. This virtualization will enable efficient and reliable deployment of network services. NFV can enable rapid network expansion, cost reduction, and flexibility for quick service delivery [68]. However, many security threats and vulnerabilities will be added because of the nature of virtualization and the intricate service dependencies. At the same time, service chaining of various VNFs makes it very difficult to determine the underlying cause of security threats [49]. Therefore, it is necessary to implement SCO along with NFV to get the maximum advantages of being virtualized. Cloud computing enables centrally managed storage in the cloud for data and programs that can be accessed anytime. The availability of data, access flexibility, and resilience are just a few benefits of cloud computing. Yet, it has limited control over high scalability, high mobility, low latency, and real-time execution. Fog computing/MEC brings networking services to the network's edge, closer to end-users, by distributing computing and data processing. While improving the network performance, cloud/MEC/fog supports novel technologies and growing trends such as NFV and SDN. [69]. Many sensors will be deployed in IoT, and vulnerabilities in these sensors make it hard to handle the security requirements

FIGURE 1. Security orchestration integration into SDN.

with a special security function. With the edge/fog computing enabled, it would be possible to launch orchestrated security services at the edge, ensuring security requirements of IoT [28]. NS enables tailored services for distinct application scenarios by slicing a single physical network into several logical networks. These networks are selected and customized according to different unique requirements to provide diverse requirements in a sustainable manner [70]. The security requirements vary according to the importance and sensitivity of the data that flows through the network. It would not be easy to establish network security in slicing and maintaining each slice's minimum security. Therefore, integration of SCO is crucial for advanced security management.

III. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN SOFTWARE DEFINED NETWORKING

A. INTRODUCTION

SDN architecture model comprises a data plane, a control plane, and an application plane. The network components that make up the data plane, such as switches and routers, process packets and flow following the controller's established rules. The logical controller lies in the control plane, translating the application requirements into appropriate forwarding rules. These rules are communicated and enforced over data plane [48]. Between the data plane and the application plane, which connects these two planes, is the control plane. SDN introduces a nice set of features such as traffic isolation, dynamic flow control, network-wide visibility, monitoring, and network programming. These could be used to enhance the functionalities of SCO and provide advanced security countermeasures. As shown in Fig. 1, SCO implementation in SDN consists of a SCO plane and security enforcement plane and user plane. Openflow switches monitor the network flow and consistently update the SDN controller. SCO can use this existing feature to get flow information through an SDN controller. At the same time, unique virtual/physical monitoring probes can be deployed in the data plane to collect network

information like network performance metrics and traffic statistics. Once the monitoring components detect malicious traffic or abnormal behavior in the flow, it will be analyzed and shared with the reaction component to take necessary action. The reaction component will look into the policy interpreter, decide on the appropriate action, and communicate with the Security Manager (SM). The network perimeter switches are dynamically reprogrammed by the SDN controller at the request of the SM to block malicious traffic flows. Traffic from an infected device can be automatically routed to a web server providing a quarantine message, and chosen switches can be instructed to block traffic flows to that portion of the network to control a virus outbreak there. With SDN, the SM must communicate with the controller for any action involving threat response, mitigation, and prevention.

B. EXISTING WORKS

Song Luo et al. [71] propose a service-oriented technique for software-defined infrastructure enabling SCO. Service-Oriented Software-Defined Security (SOSDSec) follows principles of software-defined security such as abstraction, API (Application Programming Interface) enablement, automation, and orchestration. Adel et al. [67] propose an orchestrator-based architecture that develops security applications while addressing the deficiencies of SDN architecture using network monitoring and control features. Zarca et al. [72] propose an architecture to handle channel protection and Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) in IoT networks. This novel policy-based framework includes SDN and NFV technologies, and it consists of a group of distributed SDN controllers which is responsible for managing the communication with the SDN-based network elements, which reside underneath virtual and physical infrastructure. Many research works focus on security management in IoT systems enabled by SDN and NFV [29], [48], [72], [73], [74], [75], [76], [77]. Shin et al. [78] introduces FRESKO security application framework where security measures can be defined as high-level policies such as DROP, REDIRECT or QUARANTINE, and they will be automatically translated to flow rules for OpenFlow-enabled switches. Shin et al. [79] investigate how new features provided by SDN, such as dynamic flow control, network-wide visibility, network programmability and simplified data plane, could support and enhance network security. Yoon et al. [80] conducts a feasibility study on SDN-based security applications and implements four kinds of security applications with SDN.

C. SUMMARY

SDN strengthens SCO performance by being a powerful enabler that provides complete network information to the SCO plane. SCO plane uses this information to enhance the control decisions and enforce these decisions to the required places on the data plane as flow rules through SDN. Additionally, SDN adds desirable characteristics like scalability, flexibility, and dynamism. Much research focuses on how SDN can be

used as an enabler for SCO to enhance overall network security. Some important aspects are still open when it comes to SCO in SDN. Some of them are integrating SDN monitoring information to be used at the SCO plane to make timely decisions, defining the interface between SCO plane and the SDN controller, what plugins and protocols can be used between SCO plane and SDN controller, and how the features offered by SDN could be used to enhance SCO.

Plugins and protocols could be decided according to the underlying SDN controller configurations. During the policy refinement process, which is the translation from medium-level policies to low-level policies according to the enablers' configurations, the policy interpreter invokes specific plugins offered by the security enablers provider. For example, if the OpenDayLight controller is used, specific IPTABLES plug-in and SDN plug-in could be used. Northbound APIs of SDN controller (ex, ONOS, OpenDayLight, Floodlight) and corresponding JSON models could be used to enforce relevant flow rules and flow table updates on OpenFlow switches using OpenFlow as the SDN protocol. Flow statistics and monitoring information available at the SDN controller (control plane) could be collected directly through the northbound interface of the controller as well as through open-flow switches. SDN features such as programmability and dynamic flow control can be exploited using a framework such as FRESKO [78] for creating security applications with SDN. Security orchestration enablers provider and policy interpreter modules can adapt the programming paradigm provided by FRESKO and adjust plug-in and configurations according to security applications. However, how SDN security application affects throughput, latency, and forwarding speed has not been thoroughly studied, and most of the studies are limited to prototype or test bench implementation and far from real-world scenarios.

IV. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN NETWORK FUNCTION VIRTUALIZATION

A. INTRODUCTION

Since these VNFs are not bound to a specific hardware platform, network services may now be centrally managed, dynamically moved, and deployed throughout the network as needed. Most security applications, such as anti-malware, data leakage prevention, and firewalls, can be introduced as VSFs, leveraging the functionalities of NFV. Making use of the flexibility of NFV, compromised network elements can be easily isolated from other network elements through security zones and traffic steering [49]. NFV architectural framework contains multiple functional components such as NFV Management and Orchestrator (NFV-MANO), Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI), VNFs, EMS, and Operations/Business Support System (OSS/BSS). NFVI provides all of the hardware and software resources needed to deploy VNFs. The hardware resources comprise computing, storage, and network components that give VNFs access to processing, storage, and communication through a virtualization layer.

Software packages known as VNFs can implement network functions utilizing the NFVI-provided infrastructure. A VNF runs over the NFVI, and an EMS manages the VNF [81].

NFV MANO includes three main functional blocks. They are NFV orchestrators, VNF managers, and VIM. NFV orchestrator is in charge of instantiating the life cycle management of these services. The NFV orchestrator also handles authorization for resource requests and global resource management. The VNF manager is responsible for instantiating, updating, scaling, and terminating VNFs and their life cycle management. It also executes jobs such as incident reporting and coordination among NFVI components. VIM is responsible for managing the interaction of VNFs with NFVI. The primary responsibility of VIM is to manage and allocate NFVI resources like storage, computing, and other network resources among VNFs. It also conducts performance analysis of NFVI while collecting and forwarding the performance and other metrics [82].

Management of the NFV environment through automation and orchestration is one of the primary goals of ETSI NFV. This goal could only be achieved by integrating SCO as an essential component of NFV orchestration. However, SCO has to expand further from the NFV environment to cover E2E network security [83]. Security can be considered an E2E service (security as a service) similar to other E2E services. Network Service Descriptor (NSD) provides a basis to deploy and configure E2E network services automatically, including security. SCO does not need to work standalone in NFV. It can use the already existing mechanisms, components and capabilities of NFV as defined by ETSI NFV MANO. SCO should ensure secure management and placement of VSFs over the virtualized infrastructure. VSFs are VNFs that are configured to act as a security function with a specific set of security functionalities. As a result, the VNF/VSF manager may deploy NSFs as other VNFs, following the specifications of the NSD. NFV manager does not differentiate between VNF and VFS and is unaware of VSF's particular security functionality. Following the same principle, the NFV orchestrator connects VSFs with non-security-related VNFs and brings them together to provide E2E network service.

Already existing VNF workflow management defined by ETSI NFV MANO [84] can be extended to achieve E2E SO through SCO. As shown in Fig. 2, SCO implementation in NFV consists of a SCO plane and security enforcement plane and user plane. The SM requests VSF management by sending the configuration to the NFV MANO via the service orchestrator using NSD when necessary. NFV MANO asks the VNF manager to instantiate the VNF, and VIM does instantiation deployment. Then, the VNF manager configures the basic configurations to the particular VNF. Once the VNF manager completes the VNF instantiation, deployment, and basic configuration, it sends an ACK to the NFV orchestrator. Then, the NFV orchestrator configures application-level parameters. After that NFV orchestrator asks the SM to configure VSF application-level parameters. The SM configures the VSF application level parameter to the VSF through a Element

FIGURE 2. Security orchestration integration into NFV.

Manager (EM) or a Security-EM (SEM). After that, the SM again ACK the NFV orchestrator, and the NFV orchestrator configures the connectivity. The SM can manage VSFs directly or through a SEM. The SM can not manage security functions in the NFVI itself. Therefore, the SM should be able to configure and manage these security functions through well-defined interfaces.

B. EXISTING WORKS

The work [83] introduces a security orchestrator in the context of ETSI NFV reference architecture. Authors extend the same workflow in ETSI MANO for the deployment of VNF to deploy and manage VSFs through a security orchestrator on top of the ETSI NFV reference architecture. A few research works focus on the security management of SDN/NFV-enabled/aware IoT systems [48], [72], [73], [74], [75], [76], [77]. Authors have used the ANASTACIA [85] reference architecture as a baseline and extended the work towards empowering networks consisting of IoT systems to make autonomous decisions and enable dynamic security reaction capabilities. A policy-based security framework for dynamic management of AAA and channel protection VSFs in IoT networks enabled with SDN/NFV is proposed in work [72], [74]. Pablo et al. [86] propose a framework that secures virtualized, multi-tenant IoT traffic using an autonomic control loop with effective 5G-based traffic filtering. Authors claim that this work paves the path to self-organizing networking capabilities that are highly desirable. An innovative NFV/SDN-based zero-touch security management system is proposed by Ana et al. [51] for the automatic configuration, management, and deployment of lightweight VSF in MEC Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV). After conducting a threat analysis in the context of NFV, Montida et al. [49] provide a design framework for NFV-based service orchestration and security management. Aapo et al. [87] implement a testbed

for SCO in an NFV environment and demonstrate how an intelligent response to security attacks can be realized in a way that these attacks can be prevented and mitigated. Basile et al. [88], [89] introduces a framework to automatically enforce security policies in NFV networks, considering the dynamic nature of the network. Moreover, the authors claim that this framework needs only slight modifications to the current NFV architecture.

C. SUMMARY

NFV improves flexibility and scalability in network control by decoupling network functions from hardware. In NFV, many security functions can be deployed as VSF, such as vAAA, vFirewalls, vChannelProtection, vIDS, or vIoTHoneynet. There is a requirement for a framework that can take charge of, manage, and orchestrate VNF architecture, adhering to the complex security requirements in an automated way. SCO can fill this gap and enable central security management by reusing existing NFV infrastructure and functionalities. However, some challenges need to be addressed when it comes to SCO in NFV. A few of them are as follows: (i) Defining the interface between NFVO MANO and SCO plane, (ii) what plug-ins and protocols could be used, (iii) how the features offered by NFV architecture, such as on-demand scalability, mobility support, and flexible network service provisioning, could be used to enhance the performance of SCO. (iv) How to ensure the protection of management traffic, software integrity and data in a multi-vendor NFV environment. (v) How to guarantee trust management between different NFV entities.

Plug-ins and protocols could be used according to underlying implementation and configurations. For example, a virtual router running on a NETOPEER NETCONF can be configured using a NETCONF client that introduces the iptables configuration in a YANG model, which is a part of the SM (SCO plane) [48]. During the policy refinement process, translation from medium-level policies for a generic packet filter should be translated into a valid iptables configuration file. OPENMANO framework provides open vim (reference implementation of an NFV VIM), openmano: reference implementation of an NFV-O (Network Functions Virtualization Orchestrator) and openmano-gui: web GUI to interact with openmano server [90]. Openmano offers a northbound interface based on REST API, where VNF services such as configuration of VNF templates and instances. This northbound interface can be utilized by the SCO plane to enforce VSF into the underlying network by using relevant plug-ins during the medium to low-level policy translation. A central credential manager and a trust manager could be introduced to the SCO plane to manage trust and cryptographic protection in NFV. As with SDN, the effect of enabling security services through NFV has not been thoroughly studied, and implementations are far from real-world scenarios. The scalability of SCO in NFV need to be researched considering the conflict resolution of policies, resource availability and impact on the services offered.

FIGURE 3. Security orchestration integration into NS.

V. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN NETWORK SLICING

A. INTRODUCTION

Network slicing leverages technologies such as SDN and NFV to facilitate multiple virtual networks on a shared physical infrastructure. These virtual networks are called slices and are customized to provide a specific service category. The key features of NS are automation, isolation, customization, elasticity, programmability, hierarchical abstraction and E2E service delivery [91], [92]. SCO can use the features enabled by NS to optimize and ensure the security of the slices through dedicated network functions, resources and service chain configurations. In addition, the SCO framework can manage the security of all slices and services through the Network Slice Manager (NSM), detecting, preventing and mitigating security threats and responding to security breaches [93]. The isolation of slices prevents the attackers from moving. SCO framework can deploy customized security controls over a slice and set different security levels according to the Security Service Level Agreements (SSLA).

As shown in Fig. 3, the SCO implementation in NS consists of a SCO plane and a security enforcement plane. The security enforcement plane can be divided into control and management domain and various network slices. Monitoring probes are initiated by the SCO framework and deployed in the slices to obtain useful metrics, and abnormal behaviors of traffic correspond to each slice. At the same time, the monitoring component can receive helpful information from the VNF manager and SDN controller via the NSM. Once the slice instance has been activated, the NSM must provide the SCO framework with monitoring functions to check that SSLA can be fulfilled. Once abnormal behavior or threat is detected, monitoring information passes the analysis to the reaction module. Then, it decides on the countermeasures to be deployed, which are forwarded to the SM. The SM evaluates the policies and rules stored in the policy repository and

decides on the appropriate measures and resource allocation. It communicates with the provider of the security enablers in order to enforce the corresponding enablers in the slice via the NSM and the SDN controller. In the meantime, the SM must assess the fulfillment of the SSLAs and act accordingly to allocate the limited resources to the various slices deployed. If the slices span across different operators (multi-domain), managers at global and local level might be required to ensure that the SCO framework fulfills the SSLAs across different domains.

B. EXISTING WORKS

To support slice security throughout its life cycle, Blanc et al. [93] have developed an integrated security architecture that leverages the virtualization/software infrastructure. Khettab et al. [94] propose an architecture that utilizes both SDN and NFV to secure a network slice on demand while supporting flexibility and elasticity as well as resource allocation. Martini et al. [95] examines how security challenges in NS related to management and orchestration within the ETSI NFV architecture framework can be addressed. A framework for streamlining SCO in a federated NS system is presented by Shalitha et al. [96] to support effective security management in 5G and beyond networks. Ortiz et al. [97] present a security framework in the context of INSPIRE-5Gplus [98] that specifically addresses two key aspects such as SSLAs and liability management. Shalitha et al. [99] presents a novel Security as a Service (SECaaS) solution with NS for local 5G operators. The authors introduce a dedicated security slice and a security function repository to manage security functions in a NS environment.

C. SUMMARY

Providing security in NS-supported networks is difficult due to the dynamic nature of NS and slice-specific security requirements. The SCO framework must be robust and adaptable to these requirements to ensure E2E security. There are some particular challenges associated with SCO in NS. The design of interface between the NSM and the SCO planes, the verification of SSLA compliance, the optimal allocation of resources according to the SSLAs and ensuring the E2E security of slices spanning multiple domains are just some of the issues that require thorough attention. The SM can check the fulfillment of the SSLA via NSM. A cross-domain and cross-integration fabric, as proposed in ESTI's ZSM framework [53], [98] could solve most of the problems related to interface definitions, intercommunication and E2E security orchestration that span multiple administrative domains. In the SCO plane, a policy and SSLA management block could be introduced to be responsible for defining the SSLA based on policies and real-time monitoring of the SSLA via NSM and other interfaces provided by the framework. The policy and SSLA management block can invoke a SM in the event of a breach of the SSLA. Maintaining slice isolation while providing E2E security, the overhead caused by security operations and the impact on QoS due to SCO functions must be

thoroughly investigated in order to successfully realize SCO in NS.

VI. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN MULTI-ACCESS EDGE COMPUTING, FOG, AND CLOUD COMPUTING FOR 5G TECHNOLOGIES

A. INTRODUCTION

Computing paradigms involve significant security concerns about the confidentiality and integrity of the data processed due to the sharing of the execution environment. Cloud user lacks control over the centralized cloud infrastructure [100]. MEC distributes the cloud computing capabilities to the edge, improving spectral efficiency and data locality and reducing latency. At the same time, MEC improves the flexibility of deploying innovative context-specific functionalities close to the user rapidly [51]. Cloud/MEC servers are exposed to attacks and security threats that degrade the QoS, user experience, and reliability [101]. Keeping these safe against attacks is vital and complex. After detecting a threat, the incident response must be immediate, and mitigation actions should be deployed fast. Computing resources are limited and expensive [28]. Therefore, these security mechanisms should consume minimal resources so that their overhead should have the most negligible impact on the QoS of legitimate end-users. There should be an intelligent and automated mechanism to select and deploy the most suitable security solutions on a cloud and resource-constrained MEC/fog node. This process consists of selecting suitable enablers, allocating resources, initiating incident response/mitigation action according to the SLA, and terminating security service immediately once the purpose has been served.

SCO is well suited to be implemented in all computing paradigms by leveraging NFV, SDN, and Service Function Chaining (SFC). SCO can dynamically instantiate, modify, scale, and release VSFs on demand. A protection system that successfully secures centralized/edge servers meeting all of the requirements above can be developed because of SCO's flexibility. As shown in Fig. 4, SCO implementation in cloud/MEC computing consists of an SCO plane and a security enforcement plane. Since there are enough computing resources, all the components related to SCO can be kept in one place. When it comes to resource-constrained Fog nodes, the management components such as SCO plane, as in Fig. 5, SDN controller, and NFV-MANO can be deployed in the centralized data centre or MEC node, which is closer to the fog node and provides the service to multiple nodes. It is possible to deploy VNF/VSF as containers, which use fewer resources. VNFs deployment as containers will improve instantiation time, which is considerably faster than traditional VM (Virtual Machine) based deployments.

B. EXISTING WORKS

Rojas et al. [102] propose an architecture for orchestrating the management of cloud services based on SSLAs, while Rojas et al. [103] introduce the notion of policy orchestration, which

FIGURE 4. Security orchestration integration into MEC.

FIGURE 5. Security orchestration integration into Fog.

aims to ensure security and privacy in the cloud. Kalliola et al. [104] present an architecture and implementation of a security wrapper concept for the protection of VNFs in a cloud environment. Paladi et al. [105] propose a security-enabled cloud orchestration framework for multi-cloud applications. Elaheh et al. [101], [106] propose and demonstrate a software-based security system for Content Delivery Networks (CDN) edge servers to mitigate various attacks. Vashish et al. [28], [107] propose architectures that enable the orchestration of security services on resource-constrained fog nodes. The authors of [107] use the SFC concept as a method to deploy various security tools/services in a resource-constrained edge node. The authors of [28] propose a unique architecture that can be modified with a lightweight virtualization technology such as Docker to launch dynamic security services at the edge. For

the automatic orchestration, deployment and management of lightweight VSF in MEC-UAVs, Ana et al. [51] propose an innovative NFV/SDN-aware security management framework. In Hongjia et al. [108], a cooperative defense model (CODE) against DDoS attacks using NFV and SDN capabilities for MEC is proposed. Pasika et al. [109] proposes a security architecture that provides SECaaS services in a MEC platform, considering the heterogeneous characteristics of IoT services and devices.

C. SUMMARY

Although cloud computing is not a new topic, SCO in cloud computing has not been an important topic in the research community until now. This may be due to the fact that leading Cloud Service Providers (CSP) are billion-dollar companies and have already integrated advanced security into their cloud services. Some challenges require the attention of the research community when it comes to SCO in cloud and MEC computing. SCO in cloud computing faces the following challenges. The shared responsibility model, where the CSP is responsible for the security of the underlying infrastructure and the users share the responsibility for the security of data, applications and configurations, would cause problems in orchestrating security services in the cloud [110]. The main problem with edge computing is that fewer resources are available for SCO and security overhead, which can lead to a deterioration in QoS. The definition of interfaces, plug-ins and protocols between SCO planes, both in the cloud and in the MEC, is still under investigation by the research community.

Resource optimization and the use of lightweight virtualization such as Docker are an excellent solution for resource constraints at the edge. The OpenFog reference architecture [111] offers a highly secure node management layer suitable for running SCO. Security monitoring information could also be collected via node management layer. Implementing a security wrapper could be a solution to protect the VNFs in cloud environments, as described in [104]. Here, the wrapper covers the communication links at the boundary of the enclosed area. Cloud services use different technologies and platforms and are often offered by a specific provider that relies on specific technologies and APIs. Therefore, implementing a unified security system will be difficult. In addition, the distributed and diverse nature of edge computing makes it difficult to coordinate and orchestrate security measures. Due to the decentralized nature of SCO implementation, there may be delays in responding to a security attack, updating security policies and other SCO services. The research community could focus more on the above issues in MEC/cloud computing with SCO.

VII. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN OPEN RADIO ACCESS NETWORKS (O-RAN)

A. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of network softwarization concepts and additional intelligence at the edge enable the transition of

telecommunication networks from traditional RAN to O-RAN. [52]. 5G and B5G networks will be mainly based on ORAN, which will connect critical national infrastructures, mission-critical applications and scenarios such as power grids and water supply, smart cities and factories, and intelligent transportation systems [112]. Therefore, standardizing and ensuring security in ORAN is a must for the successful implementation of future 5G and B5G networks. To integrate O-RAN into the telecommunications ecosystem, it is necessary to research and implement novel security and privacy solutions to detect, prevent and mitigate security threats associated with O-RAN. There will be multiple vendors in play, creating an open ecosystem with multiple providers. Therefore, traditional security approaches need to be upgraded to work in this open ecosystem [113]. The security risks of ORAN can be categorized as follows, taking into account the aspects of open software, radio/open interface, virtualization and intelligence [114]. To get a comprehensive understanding of the security and privacy issues in ORAN, we recommend our readers this work [64]. Some of these security vulnerabilities include attacks related to virtualization and SDN, a larger threat surface due to the decentralization of control functions, security and privacy issues with AI, and attacks due to the openness of interfaces [64], [113], [115].

There is a need for a unified security approach to address these security issues that come with O-RAN, and SCO can utilize the features introduced by O-RAN, such as virtualization, SDN, and introduced intelligence to effectively and efficiently handle the security in O-RAN. Features of SDN and NFV can be utilized to deploy, modify and terminate security functions as VNFs dynamically. SCO can enhance the introduced intelligence in O-RAN to orchestrate security operations via big data analysis, AI, and ML [64]. As a result, closed-loop responses to security threats can be automatically executed. Log monitoring and management can also be automated using approaches such as SbD (Security by Design). Since different vendors are contributing to O-RAN, those might have different security configurations. However, depending on the application and use case, the required security level, which is defined in the SSLA, could be varied, and the SCO framework needs to step up and ensure the satisfaction of SSLAs [116]. At the same time, proper standardization of security policies and dynamic adjustment according to the security levels are needed.

B. EXISTING WORKS

Pawani et al. [116] discussed an XAI-based green security architecture for resilient O-RAN in 6G. The authors emphasize the automatic and dynamic adaptation of security policies considering energy efficiency and risk level. John S et al. [117] presents the MARSAL project, which aims to create a zero-trust security framework that leverages blockchains and smart contracts to support NS transactions, ML-based threat detection, and programmable SDN switches for O-RAN. Madhusanka et al. [64] suggest the use of introduced intelligence in O-RAN to automate security management through

FIGURE 6. Security orchestration integration into ORAN.

big data analytics, AI and ML. Sanaz et al. [115] propose to implement security controls in near-real-time as xApp and security controls in non-real-time as rApp at the orchestration module to enable extensive ML processing.

C. SUMMARY

O-RAN is a software-oriented architecture that is based on the QoS requirements of the use case or application and orchestrates management, configuration and resource optimization [118]. SCO can use the features of the O-RAN Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework to orchestrate security operations and ensure SLA compliance. We propose an SCO framework for O-RAN, as shown in Fig. 6, which uses the existing O-RAN framework as well as the near-real-time RIC xApps and the non-real-time RIC rApps. There, the SCO plane with heavy computing operations could be located in the SMO framework. In contrast, lightweight SCO operations such as monitoring, data analysis and policy refinement could be located at the edge near the RT RIC. SCO can utilize already defined interfaces for policy implementation and monitoring. However, it must be clarified how the SCO plane can be integrated into the SMO framework and Non-RT RIC, whereby one solution could be to implement all functions with rApp. One problem is that not all security operations are Non-RT. This could have an impact on response time and the security of mission-critical applications is at stake. The other solution could be to implement the SCO plane outside the Non-RT RIC. Interfaces, plug-ins and protocols must then be defined between the SCO plane and the gNodeB (GNB) and the near RT-RIC. Functionalities of DLT can be used to ensure trust between untrusted components and enable secure communication, e.g. blockchain-based mutual authentication and smart contracts for privacy-preserving communication. AI-enabled O-RAN could be used in SCO for intelligent security monitoring, threat assessment and intelligent policy handling. There is little work addressing SCO in O-RAN, which means that the research community has not paid enough attention to it. Proper standardization of policy definitions and interfaces plays a crucial role for successful SCO in O-RAN, which has not been done yet.

VIII. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN ZERO-TOUCH NETWORK AND SERVICE AUTOMATION

A. INTRODUCTION

ZSM framework enables full Automation of Network and Service Management and Operation (ANSMO). Softwarization technologies such as SDN/NFV, along with AI/ML and DLT combined with model-based open interfaces, offer required flexibility, scalability and other features to realize self-managing functionalities such as self-healing, self-configuration, self-optimization and self-protection [53]. One of the main challenges of ZSM is how to protect networks, data and services against security threats and attacks. Different technologies that ZSM relies on to bring full automation bring their own security issues broadening the threat landscape of ZSM. According to Evolution of 5G Cyber Threats and Security Solutions white article [119], ZSM security issues are as follows. Security issues related to Open API, security issues related to intent-based networks, security issues in closed loop automation, AI/ML-based security issues and security issues in softwarization concepts such as SDN/NFV. For further information about ZSM security and privacy issues, we suggest interested readers refer to [53], [65], [119]. Fully automated networks have their own advantages as well as disadvantages. The ZSM framework must ensure data protection when transmitting, processing and storing. At the same time, it should satisfy the SLA and provide the required level of security at all times for different services.

Integrating SCO into the ZSM framework could be a solution to all the issues mentioned above. Policy-based SCO enables automated security threat detection, recognition, prevention and mitigation using already existing infrastructure, technologies and services of ZSM [65], [120]. Satisfaction of SLA can be ensured while optimizing resource allocation. When handling E2E security, security policies must extend to multiple management domains. This would result in security policy conflicts, which could be resolved at the security orchestrator [119]. The adoption of the ZSM approach makes the enforcement of security policies one of its main challenges since security policies are now being delegated to other domains. The policy models collected from the state of the art must be extended to be able to manage multiple domains through the E2E Security Management Domain (SMD). The emergence of a higher domain creates new conflicts involving multiple domains, and the decision to resolve them must be intelligent enough to determine whether they should be resolved in the specific SMD or at the E2E level.

B. EXISTING WORKS

Ortiz et al. [97] introduce a closed-loop E2E security management and orchestration platform leveraging techniques such as ZSM, AI/ML, DLT and TEE for 5G and B5G. The authors focus on real-time SLA monitoring and management and liability management on top of ESTI's ZSM concept. Janne et al. [121] present how ML methods, a multi-dimensional statistical method, and case-based reasoning could be used

FIGURE 7. Security orchestration integration into ZSM.

to develop an automated anomaly detection framework for Self Organizing Networks(SON). Othmane et al. [122] propose a fully distributed and trustworthy self-driving network framework that leverages DLT, a Programmable Data Planes (PDP) and AI. Chafika et al. [123] list down existing research and standardization work relevant to ZSM. Some of the listed work, such as [124], [125], [126], [127], [128], could be helpful in realizing a unified SCO framework for ZSM.

C. SUMMARY

Most research on the security of ZSM focuses on different areas and not on a unified security framework. SCO could be the right solution to work hand in hand with ZSM. We propose an SCO framework for ZSM that utilizes the already existing infrastructure of ZSM, as shown in Fig. 7. Even if SCO can use the existing technologies and infrastructure of ZSM, there are still some challenges that need to be overcome. A reliable mechanism should be in place to avoid security policy conflicts and resolve them in real time in the event of a conflict scenario. Ensuring compliance of SSLAs is a challenge because firstly, there should be a framework for real-time monitoring of SSLAs, which could indeed be a part of the SCO monitoring module. Then the satisfaction of the SSLA must be assessed and real-time measures must be taken according to the dynamic and complex changes of the network. Security issues related to AI could be addressed with distributed AI, e.g. federated learning [122], and privacy issues could be addressed with XAI.

Finally, Table 2 provides a literature survey of performance comparison of SCO in different domains.

IX. LESSONS LEARNED AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This section covers lessons learned, remaining research challenges, and future directions related to Section II, focusing on identifying and addressing SCO's unresolved issues.

A. LESSONS LEARNED

Functionalities and attributes of novel 5G and B5G network technologies and concepts, such as ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, NS and MEC/cloud computing, could be used to strengthen SCO in 5G and B5G networks. SCO cloud utilizes these technologies' existing mechanisms, components, and capabilities to enable E2E and zero-touch security. However, these technologies will introduce new threats and security issues that did not exist before. Therefore, securing these technologies is a cumbersome task and might potentially disrupt the SCO operation if not handled carefully (ex: SDN [131]). The objective of SCO is to leverage enabling technologies to address the security issues in 5G and B5G, including these new threats and security issues coming from enabling technologies. For example, SCO could leverage attributes of softwarization such as dynamic flow control, traffic isolation, network-wide visibility and programmability for adaptive and dynamic security management according to the specified privileges and policies. The relationship between SCO and enabling technologies could be referred to as "coexistence".

Most researchers design and implement the SCO plane as a centralized entity in their frameworks. Because of that, the SCO plane can quickly get a holistic view of the underlying network. Still, apart from all the advantages, there is a danger of a single point of failure, putting the whole network's security at risk. This problem must be thoroughly addressed, and introducing global and local SCO planes to handle security in the respective domains might be a solution [96]. These local SCO planes could be moved to the edge, given that there are enough resources and concepts like AI at the edge, distributed learning and federated learning should be exploited to improve SCO's performance. However, the Implementation of SCO comes at a cost. Since SCO uses the same resources, such as computing and spectrum. If SCO does not deploy properly, there will be an impact on the QoS of legitimate services and users, such as increased latency and reduced throughput. Currently, SCO frameworks are still evolving, and implementations are limited to research projects and test beds. Moreover, realizing a unified E2E SCO framework is also challenging due to the heterogeneity of technologies and lack of coordination in standardization. For example, integration and communication between different technology SDOs must be researched thoroughly.

As one of the main contributions of this survey, we present a unified architecture for SCO in 5G and B5G networks, considering technologies such as SDN, NFV, NS, edge/cloud computing and IoT. As shown in Fig. 8, the proposed architecture mainly relies on network. This IP/MPLS SDN networking architecture is influenced by [135]. Both the core and the edge cloud consist of a virtualized server, and v-routers/v-switches run in the server's hypervisor. The SDN controller provides the server, routers and switches to create SDN tunnels. Then the SDN controller maps these tunnels and MPLS L3 VPN creating various slices that connect the edge cloud to the core cloud.

TABLE 2. Performance Comparison of SCO in Different Domains

Feature	SCO in ORAN	SCO in ZSM	SCO in SDN	SCO in NFV	SCO in NS	SCO edge/cloud computing
Response time	Security operations performed at non-RT RIC > 1s, near zero response time at near RT-RIC (10 ms to 1s) [116]	Less (closed-loop automation, AI/ML) [53], [97]	Less (network-wide monitoring, dynamic flow control) [79], [129]	Less (could be deployed closer to the edge) [49]	Less (application-specific security services) [94]	Less (edge/fog computing), High (cloud computing) [130]
Scalability	High (V-RAN, modularity allows operators to be more flexible and allocate resources for monitoring and control, improving scalability) [64]	High (automation) [53], [97]	High (programmability) [80], [129]	High (virtualization) [49]	High (predictive auto-scaling, application-specific policies) [94]	High (lightweight virtualization) [130]
Implementation complexity	High (Due to loss of total ownership, multiple interfaces and technologies) [64], [116]	Medium (could use existing ZSM architecture) [97]	Medium (already available open source implementation (ex: ONOS, OpenDayLight, Floodlight))	Medium (could use existing ESTI NFV MANO framework, policy-based VNF orchestration) [89]	High (E2E security spans over multiple domains)	Medium (closer to the user, resource-constrained)
Security services supported	Threat detection, Threat analysis and mitigation [117]	Network traffic classification, prediction of network flow [53], [123]	Configuration of security services, and threat detection, mitigation and verification, security as a service [131]	Security as a service, vAAA, Traffic filtering, vFirewalls [130]	Security as a service, IDS, IPS, Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) [94]	Security as a service, IDPS, Traffic isolation, Authentication, Secure transmission [108], [109], [132]
Monitored entities	gNB (CU, DU and RU), SDN switches [116], [117]	SDN controller, SDN switches, VNFs, Cross/intra domain fabric	SDN controller, SDN switches, flow tables	VNFs, NFV MANO, VNF Manager, NFVI, SDN switches	Slice manager, VNFs, SDN switches [133]	Edge/cloud servers, SDN switches, VIM, VNFs [101]
Used technologies	XAI, Blockchain, PLS(Physical Layer Security), VM, Digital Twin Networks (DTN), IBN, ZSM [64], [116]	XAI, IBN, Big data analytics, Blockchain [53], [97], [123], [134]	VMs, containers, hypervisors [53]	VMs, containers, hypervisors [53]	VMs, containers, hypervisors [97]	VMs, containers, hypervisors [53]

FIGURE 8. Unified framework for security orchestration.

This unified SCO architecture represents a significant innovation in enabling SCO and addressing security challenges in 5G and B5G networks. This architecture is able to dynamically map security policies to network slices, ensuring SLA satisfaction. For example, SDN tunnels mapped to MPLS L3 VPNs enable isolated and secure network slices. This framework improves scalability, and the SCO plane can continuously monitor the compliance of SLA of each slice while ensuring that security policies are enforced consistently across heterogeneous environments. As elaborated in Fig. 9, SCO plane orchestrates and manages the security operations

FIGURE 9. Interaction/data-flow between different planes.

and services of the underlying network. The user plane defines the security policies at the highest level and monitors the network. The underlying network is an enabler for the SCO plane, which provides monitoring instances, enforces security measures and facilitating SCO.

B. REMAINING RESEARCH PROBLEMS

- How to implement SCO at the resource-constrained edge successfully, how to support decentralized SCOs?
- How can the functionalities/attributes of different 5G and beyond network technologies be optimally integrated

TABLE 3. Summary of Related Works: SCO in 5G and B5G

Ref	Description	SCO in 5G and B5G					
		ORAN	ZSM	SDN	NFV	Edge	NS
[115]	Discussed AI-enabled ORAN research directions, opportunities, and challenges in 6G security.	✓					
[116]	Presented an XAI-based green security architecture for dynamic adjustment of security policies in ORAN.	✓					
[117]	Discussed orchestrating network resources in B5G for E2E service delivery, including security.	✓				✓	✓
[71]	Presented a service-oriented approach for SCO in SDN abstracting security controls as services.			✓			
[67]	Proposed a security orchestration framework leveraging SDN control and monitoring.			✓			
[72]	Proposed a policy-based architecture to handle AAA and channel protection.			✓	✓		
[74]	Presented a situational-aware policy-based security architecture in SDN/NFV-enabled IoT networks.			✓	✓		
[73]	Proposed a comprehensive SCO architecture as part of the ANASTACIA H2020 project.			✓	✓		
[48]	Introduced a policy-based architecture using SDN/NFV mechanisms for IoT security.			✓	✓		
[75]	Developed an SCO architecture for network protection using SDN/NFV technologies.			✓	✓		
[106]	Proposed a dynamic SCO system for edge security and management of function chains.					✓	
[97]	Presented an intelligent 5G security framework leveraging AI, ML, and DLT for closed-loop E2E SCO.		✓				✓
[29]	Proposed a zero-touch SCO framework ensuring optimal VSF allocation in SDN/NFV-aware IoT setups.			✓	✓		

and used in SCO to deliver the stringent security requirements of 5G and B5G use cases?

- How to coordinate the implementation of a multi-domain, fully automated E2E intelligent network and security management framework for 5G and B5G?
- How to develop and realize cross-technology SCO and define common interfaces to communicate?
- How to address QoS degradation due to SCO services?

C. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

When launching the security services at the edge, e.g., fog nodes, constrained resources are a substantial problem [51]. Using lightweight virtualization technology such as docker, hypervisor, and containers to launch VSF at the edge is another research direction to which less attention has been paid so far [28], [136]. The dynamic allocation of resources (e.g. Docker containers [136]) for various security services must be examined here, taking the SLA into account. Security services must be created, managed with optimal resource allocation and destroyed as soon as the job is completed, freeing the allocated resources for another service. Moreover, security issues related to lightweight virtualization, such as runtime anomalies due to shared resources and API security, should be addressed within the SCO framework. Holistic and context-aware security frameworks are required to enable the orchestration of SDN controllers, and NFV managers.

The use of NFV/SDN capabilities in IoT environments is already well advanced [29], [48], [72], [72], [73], [74], [74], [76], [86]. Nevertheless, there is still room for further work, such as exploring the smooth integration and interaction of technologies from the perspective of SCO. The lightweight communication bus called domain integration fabric introduced with INSPIRE-5Gplus, [97] could be used to integrate different domains and facilitate communication between them. There is a need to invent highly-expressive and universal security policy languages and plug-ins compatible with current technologies and the technologies yet to come [72]. Proper standardization is the way forward to achieve E2E SCO, which spans multiple domains consisting of multiple technologies. The right balance between SCO operations and other network services must be found to address the

impact on QoS due to SCO services. Ensuring compliance with SLAs and SSLAs while optimizing dynamic resource allocation is a necessity. At the same time, optimizing and streamlining the SCO operation in a way that does not cause unnecessary overhead is also important. Moreover, the optimization of supporting technologies such as ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, NS and cloud/edge computing will have a major impact on QoS. All of the above require extensive research and collaboration between the research community, industry and standardization organizations. Table 3 provides a summary of related works of SCO in 5G and B5G.

X. CONCLUSION

The rapidly evolving network landscape, which includes advanced technologies such as ORAN, ZSM, SDN, NFV, cloud/MEC computing, and NS, is becoming increasingly complex, especially when it comes to meeting the diverse needs of users. Under these conditions, SCO proves to be a centralized solution that takes advantage of virtualization and programmable networks. Its integration with 5G and B5G technologies is crucial for improving network security. In this article, we have highlighted the importance of SCO in 5G and B5G and described the processes and strategies for its effective integration. A comprehensive literature review is presented that highlights the possible ways and solutions to integrate SCO despite current and foreseeable technical challenges. We have also highlighted key design insights, identified unresolved research questions, and outlined future research directions.

The 6G technology envisages extreme connectivity among its billions of devices to tackle the requirements of automation in its vast digital infrastructure. Cyber intrusions targeting the threat vectors of this multi-vendor, multi-operator environment, along with privacy, integrity, and availability of services, contrive a complex yet aggressive hindrance to the seamless service requirements of 6G. To address this, an autonomous solution is a mandatory requisite. Thus, SCO stands to facilitate the 6G infrastructure with advanced threat detection, risk assessment, remediation, and optimally allocating security resources to manage the service level guarantees. The resiliency of 6G can be enhanced with AI-driven proactive

defense strategies deployed promptly by the SCO. This will lead to minimal down time of services with less probability for breaches. These capabilities of the SCO, make it the most logical security solution for 6G prominence.

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